

Supplementary Material: Experimental and computational analysis of REM sleep distributed cortical activity in mice

Figure S1: A: raw signal. B: Delta cycle detection, first the signal is segmented into cycles, first threshold detection (blue), second threshold detection (purple). In green are the validated delta cycles C: Delta bouts are shown in darker green

Table S1: Delta overlap statistical analysis

	Mean	Standard Deviation	SE of Mean
S1_on_S2	36,089 %	17,872 %	1,631 %
S2_on_S1	51,874 %	20,549 %	1,876 %
S1_on_M1	9,621 %	16,42 %	1,499 %
M1_on_S1	26,413 %	34,845 %	3,181 %
S2_on_M1	7,884 %	13,916 %	1,27 %
M1_on_S2	21,479 %	32,374 %	2,955 %

Table S1-1: Delta overlap accross the cortex, One way ANOVA

	MeanDiff	t Value	Prob
S2_on_S1 S1_on_S2	0,15784	5,08616	<0,0001
S1_on_M1 S1_on_S2	-0,26468	-8,52876	<0,0001
S1_on_M1 S2_on_S1	-0,42252	-13,61492	<0,0001
M1_on_S1 S1_on_S2	-0,09676	-3,11788	0,02842
M1_on_S1 S2_on_S1	-0,2546	-8,20404	<0,0001
M1_on_S1 S1_on_M1	0,16792	5,41088	<0,0001
S2_on_M1 S1_on_S2	-0,28205	-9,08847	<0,0001
S2_on_M1 S2_on_S1	-0,43989	-14,17464	<0,0001
S2_on_M1 S1_on_M1	-0,01737	-0,55972	1
S2_on_M1 M1_on_S1	-0,18529	-5,97059	<0,0001
M1_on_S2 S1_on_S2	-0,1461	-4,70778	<0,0001
M1_on_S2 S2_on_S1	-0,30394	-9,79394	<0,0001
M1_on_S2 S1_on_M1	0,11858	3,82097	0,00217
M1_on_S2 M1_on_S1	-0,04934	-1,5899	1
M1_on_S2 S2_on_M1	0,13595	4,38069	2,04E-04

Table S1-2: Delta overlap Means Comparisons

Delta power during delta/non-delta periods of S1				
Effect	F	p	pi.05	ges
state	7.692	9.00e-03	*	0.176
area	15.573	1.34e-05	*	0.464
state:area	3.955	2.80e-02	*	0.180

Delta power during delta/non-delta periods of S2				
Effect	F	p	pi.05	ges
state	8.128	7.00e-03	*	0.184
area	14.384	2.56e-05	*	0.444
state:area	2.333	1.12e-01		0.115

Delta power during delta/non-delta periods of M1				
Effect	F	p	pi.05	ges
state	9.489	0.004000	*	0.209
area	8.925	0.000712	*	0.331
state:area	0.773	0.469000		0.041

Table S1-3: Two way ANOVA about the changes in Delta power according to the Delta/non-delta bouts ('state' here) and the area

Delta power during delta/non-delta periods of S1			
	Value	p	pi.05
M1	1.943	0.100000	
S1	7.818	0.000231	*
S2	2.364	0.056000	

Delta power during delta/non-delta periods of S2			
	Value	p	pi.05
M1	2.204	0.070	
S1	2.652	0.038	*
S2	4.901	0.003	*

Delta power during delta/non-delta periods of M1			
	Value	p	pi.05
M1	7.228	0.000356	*
S1	6.060	0.000916	*
S2	2.815	0.030000	*

Table S1-4: Bonferroni corrections for ANOVA results

Figure S2: Classical model results with homogeneous adaptation (A): Power spectrum for the four adaptation values presented in D (B): Histogram of the mean firing rate at each nodes for excitatory and inhibitory populations (in Blue and Red respectively) for a W model with $b=5$. (C): Same as B but for the SWS model with $b=60$. (D): Mean signal and its deviation for the different value of adaptation discussed.

Figure S3: Heterogeneous REM-model vs REM shuffled. Left and Right panels represent the same aspects in two distinct models; the heterogeneous REM-model and its randomised equivalent the REM shuffled. (A/D): Topology of the adaptation parameter in the model. While a clear organisation can be seen in A, it is not the case of D where the setting of b is randomised. (B/E): Power spectrum of the three populations with different adaptation in each model. There is the same number of nodes that participate in the different populations of the two panels. (C/E): Example LFP signals in the two models. As we can see in F, the b values of the sites of interest are randomised.

Figure S4: Long simulation example: (A) 20 second of example signal from the five nodes of interest (from top to bottom: M1, mPFC, dCA1, S2, S1) in each hemisphere. Delta cycles detected are in red, Delta bouts in green and non-Delta bouts in black. In blue are the non-scored non-delta part. (B)Top: scatterplot of the decay and rise time fall Delta cycles detected across the 104nodes in the 1min long simulation of REMSsleep. Bottom: violinplot of the rise/decay symmetry for the nodes with different adaptation level (from left to right b=5, 30, 60). (C): Average power spectrum for nodes with adaptation of 5 (light blue), 30 (blue) and 60 (dark blue) for all delta bouts (plain line) or for all non-delta bouts (dashed line).

	B=5 (74 nodes)		B=30 (18 nodes)		B=60 (12 nodes)	
	Delta	Non-Delta	Delta	Non-Delta	Delta	Non-Delta
Number of bouts	238	1125	89	275	90	160
Average number of bouts/node	3.21	15.2	4.94	15.2	7.5	13.33
Mean duration of a bout (ms)	1451.46	2595.97	1458.56	2327.01	1682.49	2021.13
Mean duration of whole simulation (ms)	4671.43	39481	7216.72	35566.78	12626.17	26961.67

Table S2: Quantitative assessment of Delta activity in the REM whole brain model.

Figure S5: Method of stimulus experiment in the model. (A): Representation of the temporal repartition of the simulations in the protocol. Each stimulus lasts 20ms and is repeated every 1.25 ± 0.25 seconds. (B): Peak amplitude of the Stimulus Evoked Potential (SEP) according to the strength of the stimulus (connection weight). On the Y axis is the amplitude of the response peak observed in the stimulated region. On the X axis is the connection weight between the stimulus source and the stimulated region. Both axis are shown in log. The three panels show the responses values in the different model state (W-model, SWS-model, REM-model from left to right). (C): Time to the peak of SEP according to the strength of the stimulus (connection weight). On the Y axis is the time to the first peak response observed in the stimulated region. On the X axis is the connection weight between the stimulus source and the stimulated region. Both axis are shown in log. The three panels show the responses values in the different model state. (D): Response amplitude (average amplitude of LFP signal 0.5 sec after the stimulus / 0.5 sec before), according to the connection strength between the external node and its target, here S1. Each panel shows the response in a different state, in Asynchronous Irregular (AI), Slow Wave (SW) and REM (i, ii and iii, corresponding to the biological state of W, SWS and REM respectively), and the different curves shows the response evoked in S1 (dark blue), S2 (blue) and M1 (light blue)

Figure S6: Kinetics of the response to stimulation. This figure shows the temporal evolution of the model in response to stimulation in the three different states. Each line shows one of the states and each panel shows one period manually selected: Panel 1: Response deflection. This panel shows the first part of the stimulus response, up to 42ms after the stimulation, we can see the large deflection of the signal in S1. Similar in duration, the amplitude vary according to the state. Panel 2: Second part of the response. This panel shows how the first response end as well as the the speed to the return to ‘averaged’ value is dependant of the model state. Panle 3: Complete picture of the response observed in the different areas.

Figure S7: Dynamical response to stimulation in S1. This figure shows the different results of the experimental data analysis (left) and the model (right) presented in the article. (A): Representation of the experimental data presented in the column below. (B): Power spectrum observed for the 5 recorded areas. (C) Example of experimental recording REM LFP signals (D): Representation of the cortex model presented in the column below. (E): Power spectrum observed for the different adaptation values. (F) Example showing the LFP signal obtained with the REM model

Figure S8: Cortical LFP recordings in REM. This figure shows the activity observed across the cortex during REM. A: 10 sec examples of LFP signals at the different recording sites. B: Normalized power spectrum. C: Comparison of normalized delta bandpower [1.5-4.5Hz] in the different areas during REM